

Reviewing Deep Learning-Based Feature Extractors in a Novel Automotive Slam Framework

Christos Anagnostopoulos^{1,2}, Aris S. Lalos², Petros Kapsalas³, Duong Van Nguyen³, Chrysostomos Stylios^{1,2}

¹Department of Informatics and Telecommunication, University of Ioannina, Greece

²Industrial Systems Institute, Athena Research Center, Patras Science Park, Greece

³ Panasonic Automotive, Langen, Germany

{anagnostopoulos, lalos, stylios}@isi.gr, {petros.kapsalas, duongvan.nguye}@eu.panasonic.com

Abstract—Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), which is characterized as a core problem in autonomous vehicles, involves the estimation of the vehicle’s position and the concurrent building of the map of the environment. The use of deep learning-based feature extractors has gain increasing popularity since they possess the ability to extract reliable and repeatable features from raw sensor data. However, the performance of deep learning-based approaches varies depending on the application, environmental conditions, and the type of implemented technology. In this paper, we evaluate the performance of several deep learning-based feature extractors integrated into a SLAM system, using as input real and synthetic data, which implement common odometry problems. To our knowledge, this is the first work that benchmarks the accuracy of deep-learning based algorithms in estimating the vehicle’s trajectory in specific odometry corner cases.

Index Terms—SLAM, Deep Learning, Feature Extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

Simultaneous localization and mapping is very important for the localization and the achievement or persistent autonomy for autonomous vehicles especially in situations where there is no prior knowledge of the environment. SLAMs that use as input only images (VSLAM), have gained extreme popularity over the last years and have made great progress on providing accurate systems that can localize autonomous agents. The extraction of reliable, robust and repeatable feature points is of utmost importance for these systems. Over the last years deep learning-based feature extractors are starting to substitute model-based components.

We evaluate the performance of seven feature extractors, one model-based and six deep learning-based, on two publicly available datasets, one including real data and one including synthetic. We benchmark their accuracy in terms of the error in estimating the vehicles’s trajectory. We also evaluate their robustness in various challenging scenarios, such as low-light conditions and dynamic scenes. Furthermore, we analyze their efficiency in terms of the computational requirements in terms of execution time.

In the context of this work, we have realized a novel framework by integrating a modular SLAM system with a stack of automotive simulators and the Robotic Operating System (ROS) [1] for realizing simulation scenarios related

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with connected autonomous vehicles, federated learning and lifelong training. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized in the following bullets:

- Development of a novel framework that integrates a modular SLAM system with an automotive simulator stack and ROS. This framework enables testing of deep-learning based front ends in the context of federated and lifelong learning scheme.
- Extensive evaluation of popular algorithms that implement deep learning-based features extractors integrated into SLAM systems operating under challenging conditions.
- Evaluation of the aforementioned approaches on real datasets that realize realistic odometry corner cases

The remaining sections of the paper are structured as follows: Section II delves into Visual Odometry and focuses specifically on feature extractors, Section III provides a detailed description of the experimental setup, Section IV presents the results of the experiments conducted, and finally, in Section V, we draw conclusions and summarize our findings.

II. VISUAL ODOMETRY

Visual Odometry (VO) can be described as the process of estimating the motion of the moving agent by taking as input only a sequence of images acquired by a fixed camera setup. Its fundamental principle is to determine the camera’s displacement and orientation with respect to its initial position by examining the discrepancies between the photographs. It is a sub case of Structure From Motion (SfM) technique with which differentiates mainly in two points: VO has to meet real-time requirements and the images are sequentially ordered.

The visual odometer by itself delivers poor results regarding vehicle’s pose estimation since, it cannot limit the trajectory drift. However, coupled with an optimization back end constitutes a system that can have impressive results. These are the two building blocks of a VSLAM system. Depending on the method that the visual odometer’s front end employs for correlating consecutive images, VSLAMs can be separated into direct and indirect systems. In order to determine the camera’s translation using the indirect technique, a number of representative key points is chosen by each frame. These key points must then be detected and matched in subsequent images. It is very popular since it

not only conserves the image’s key information but also is more efficient regarding computational resources. The direct technique, which operates directly on pixel intensity and uses all of the image’s information without any preprocessing, is more robust in a setting with sparse texture. Both the indirect approach and the direct method have received a lot of attention and have evolved to varying degrees. We are going to focus into indirect systems since we are studying the performance of systems that have adopted a deep learning-based feature extractors in their front end.

A. Traditional Feature Extraction

Indirect or feature-based VSLAMs follow a common pipeline which includes the detection, the extraction, and the matching of geometrical features, which can be points, lines or planes, from images, lines or planes. The product of the previous step is utilized for the estimation of the camera’s pose and the creation of a map of the surrounding environment. Initially feature detection and extraction employed techniques that were searching for corners, like Harris [2] and FAST [3]. The fact that corners frequently could not provide robust features motivated researchers to look for more solid local image features. Modern VSLAM approaches are based on feature extraction algorithms, like SIFT [4], SURF [5], and ORB [6], that select more robust and invariant to scale features. Each keypoint is accompanied by a feature descriptor which is used for the subsequent matching. However, as it has already been stated, geometry-based features demonstrate a high dependence on the low-level hand-designed features that do not represent well the complex environment in the real world. Moreover, they find difficulties to cope with highly dynamic environments or feature-poor environments.

B. Deep Learning Based Feature Extraction

The requirement for more robust systems and semantic perception drives the research to non-model-based techniques. Deep learning-based techniques seem like the logical evolution of VSLAM systems since they can provide more robust and high-level features. They can also learn complex and abstract features which are difficult to be extracted by hand-crafted methods. Typical deep neural networks that can be used for feature extraction are Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and autoencoders.

In the following part of this work we are going to present one geometric and six deep learning-based techniques of feature extraction and we are going to evaluate them using both real and synthetic data.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Framework

We have combined a modular, open-source Python library [7] with an integrated simulation framework [8] that utilizes ROS. This modular framework incorporates three simulators: Carla [9], an autonomous driving simulator, Sumo [10], a traffic simulator, and Artery [11], a network simulator. The

simulation framework is fully integrated, providing a comprehensive platform for testing and evaluating autonomous driving algorithms.

Fig. 1. Basic components of the framework.

Our implemented framework supports the generation of multi-modal sensor data and is compatible with ROS, allowing for easy implementation of decentralized applications. Additionally, it can facilitate lifelong multi-stage training and federated learning. This feature enables us to test lifelong k federated learning-based deep feature components in automotive SLAM applications.

Figure 1 depicts the fundamental elements of our framework. The simulation stack on the left generates raw data, which is translated into ROS compatible messages via the ROS bridge. On the right, there are N agents, which follow a predetermined procedure consisting of M rounds. For each round $j \in [1, M]$, each agent trains a local model using its locally available dataset, optionally performs post-processing operations such as compression and encryption, and then transmits the trained local model Lk_j , where $k \in [1, N]$, to the server. The server can be located on-premises or in the cloud. Subsequently, the server receives these models, applies a fusion policy to them, and sends back the new global model G_1 to the clients. The common global model transmitted by the server serves as a starting point for every client at the beginning of each round.

A part of this framework has been used for the evaluation of the feature extractor algorithms described in the following chapter. The algorithms are integrated into a Visual Odometry pipeline, which resembles a basic SLAM system. It includes a feature extractor, feature matcher, keyframe management, and a bundle adjustment component. The matching of keypoints between consecutive frames is achieved through a k -nearest neighbors matcher. It is important to note that the VSLAM system is not designed to meet real-time requirements. However, its modular design enables easy interchangeability of the components under test.

Finally, regarding the hardware resources used, all the experiments were executed on the same platform with an NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti GPU, an Intel Core i7-8700 CPU, and 32GB of RAM.

B. Algorithms under Evaluation

The Scale-Invariant Feature Transform or SIFT [6], was invented by Lowe in 1999. According to this method the image is firstly convolved with Gaussian filters at different scales resulting to a set of successive Gaussian-blurred images. The keypoints are detected on the minima/maxima of the Difference of Gaussian (DOG) that take place in different scales. Candidate keypoints are filtered out by interpolating nearby data to determine the accurate position, discarding low-contrast candidates and dropping high edge response. Each keypoint is assigned to one or more orientations which derive from the local gradient directions. The final step is the calculation of the keypoint descriptor which is a 3D spatial histogram of the image gradients.

TABLE I
DEEP LEARNING BASED FEATURE EXTRACTORS

Extractor	Network	Type	Parameters
SuperPoint [12]	VGG	self-supervised	1.2 M
R2D2 [13]	L2-Net	self-supervised	486 K
ContextDesc [14]	ResNet-50	supervised	23.9
DISK [15]	U-Net	supervised	1.1M
D2-Net [16]	VGG	supervised	7.6M
Key.Net [17]	CNN	self-supervised	1.3M

SuperPoint [12] uses a common VGG [18] based encoder for producing a common representation of the original image downscaled by a factor of eight. The product of this operation is then fed to two parallel branches that produce simultaneously pixel-level locations of interest points and 256-bit long associated descriptors in one forward pass. The proposed framework is self-supervised, and it doesn't extract patches, but it rather operates on full-sized images. It also introduces the stage of Homographic Adaption in which pseudo ground truth labels are produced by a network trained on online-generated synthetic images of basic geometric shapes. Then, the annotated dataset is used for training the final model which is based on Siamese training scheme. According to this procedure, a pair of synthetically warped images, which are related by a randomly selected homography, is used as an input. For both images we are aware of the ground truth interest point locations and the ground truth correspondences. The training loss is the sum of two intermediate losses, one for the featured detector and one for the descriptor. The first one is a fully convolutional cross-entropy loss and the latter one is based on a weighted hinge loss.

Another work that like Superpoint uses a shared backbone and produces simultaneously interest points and descriptors is the Repeatable and Reliable Detector and Descriptor or R2D2 [13]. However, in this case the backbone is a fully convolutional network based on L2-Net [19] in which the last convolutional layer is replaced by three smaller layers. The 128 dimensional output of this network is used as an input to three parallel branches that generate three outputs. The first branch is a l_2 normalization layer which generates dense D-size descriptors for each pixel. The second branch includes an element-wise square operation, a convolutional

1×1 layer and a softmax activation for producing reliability and confidence values for each descriptor, while the last branch produces a repeatability map. Concerning the loss function for repeatability the goal is the maximization of the cosine similarity on local patches between the repeatability maps of a pair of images with known correspondences. The loss based on the maximization of the Average Precision metric is used for the part of reliability. The network was trained in both synthetic and real data using style transfer techniques to address issues like drastic illumination changes.

TABLE II
KITTI DATA RMSE ATE

Extractor	KITTI Sequences			
	03	04	09	10
SIFT	1.12	0.29	47.54	4.03
SP	2.7	0.65	33.2	11.19
R2D2	33.97	0.29	47.85	failed
CD	2.84	0.12	31.63	7.5
DISK	failed	0.28	54.42	23.93
D2-Net	33.97	failed	failed	failed
Key.Net	1.07	0.22	55.06	5.12

In [15] Tyszkiewicz et al. presented a method for extracting local features with policy gradient called DISK. More, specifically, a backbone network based on the U-Net [20] architecture takes an image as input and produces keypoint heatmaps and dense descriptors. The keypoint heatmap is divided into smaller patches and one keypoint is selected per patch using a softmax function, just like SuperPoint. When the set of the extracted features is known, each feature is associated with a l_2 – *normalized* descriptor. During the training phase, for each pair of images the l_2 distance of the descriptors is computed. To tackle the issue of matching ambiguous points due to recurring image motifs the authors adopted a relaxed cycle-consistent matching strategy. Using Reinforcement Learning principles and the ground truth, they assign positive or negative rewards to each match and finally the execute gradient descent to maximize the anticipated reward.

Fig. 2. Views from CarlaSCENES dataset

D2-Net [16] proposes an architecture which includes a CNN network which jointly estimates sparse features and descriptors of a given image. More, specifically the CNN network is based on the VGG16 architecture and pretrained in ImageNet [21] in which the final VGG block is dropped. The output of the

convolution stage is a 3D tensor F , $F \in R^{h \times w \times z}$, where $h \times w$ are the dimensions of the image and z is the size of the channels and thus the size of the descriptor. The descriptors after a stage or normalization are used for the matching of the points between two images. The same convolution product is used to extract n different detection response maps. Then for each pixel, the most preeminent channel is selected and checked whether there is a local-maximum on the particular detection map. The loss function adopted is an extension to the triple margin ranking loss which seeks to minimize the distance of the corresponding descriptors and maximize the distance of the others

Key.Net [17] combines handcrafted with learned features within a shallow multi-scale architecture. The handcrafted filters use first and second order derivatives to compute salient corner responses. From every image I they calculate I_x and I_y which are the 1st order gradients, as well as $I_x * I_y$, I_x^2 , and I_y^2 . In addition, the second order derivatives I_{xx} , I_{yy} , and I_{xy} are included in the Hessian matrix. The learned detector includes a convolutional layer and a ReLU activation function. The purpose of the handcrafted filters is to reduce the number of the total learnable parameters of the network. The authors propose a multi-scale index proposal layer for detecting keypoints that exist across a range of scales. The loss function used is the average of convariant losses from all scale levels.

The final model under review is ContextDesc [14] a feature extractor which augments feature descriptors by introducing context awareness. The framework consists of two parts, a preparation part and an augmentation part. The preparation part has a module that takes as input the image and is responsible for producing 32x32 gray-scale patches, a local feature extractor, which absorbs the patches from the previous module and produces feature descriptors, and a regional feature extractor, which is based on a ResNet-50 [22] network. The products of the preparation part are consumed by the aggregation component, which includes a visual and a geometric context encoder.

C. Datasets

KITTI [23] can be characterized as the pioneering dataset is benchmarking applications related with autonomous vehicles. It consists of a large collection of images, LiDAR point clouds, IMU readings and other data captured from sensors mounted on the car. The odometry subset contains all the necessary data that can be provided to a visual SLAM algorithm for estimating the pose of the vehicle and reliably evaluating it afterwards. It includes 22 sequences of images covering different driving scenarios, like driving in highway or in urban environments. The first sequences are accompanied with the ground truth for estimating the performance of the algorithm under test.

Despite its huge popularity, KITTI does not include common odometry problems that can breach certain assumptions utilized by geometric solutions or reduce the accuracy of deep learning based techniques. CarlaSCENES [24] is a dataset that gathers challenging automotive scenarios which implement

the aforementioned conditions. More specifically, the dataset contains:

- a sequence of images depicting roads with positive or negative slope that can breach the planarity assumption employed by several algorithms,
- a sequence of images captured in a feature-poor rural environment where the ability of the algorithms to detect reliable discriminative features is examined,
- a sequence containing images captured in modifiable weather and lighting conditions in which the algorithms are examined on how they handle the alternating environmental conditions,
- a sequence of images containing moving objects that cover the 50% focus of expansion of cameras,
- a sequence captured in a long highway in which the extracted landmarks should experience larger shifts due to the high speed of the moving vehicle,
- a sequence captured by a car that follows a path including loops in an urban environment,
- and a sequence captured in a complex urban environment.

An indicative example of images included in the dataset is depicted in Figure 2.

D. Metrics

The Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE) is used to estimate the absolute drift of the estimated pose in relevance to the given ground truth. Since the two trajectories are given in two different coordinate frames and in the case of Monocular SLAM in different scales, the alignment of the two trajectories must precede the calculation of the ATE. This is executed by the Umeyama alignment algorithm [25] which results to a 3D similarity transform \mathcal{T} . Let \mathcal{P} be the estimated trajectory produced by the SLAM algorithm for n poses and \mathcal{G} the corresponding ground truth, the ATE \mathcal{E} for the frame $i \in [0, n]$ can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\mathcal{E}_i = \mathcal{G}_i^{-1} \mathcal{T} \mathcal{P}_i$$

where $\mathcal{G}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{E} \in SE(3)$ and $\mathcal{T} \in Sim(3)$ which represent the special Euclidean group and the similarity group in three dimensions respectively.

For all the time instances n , the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the ATE is:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{E}_i^2}$$

In SLAM systems, the execution time of deep learning-based feature extractors is crucial. Faster inference times enable real-time behaviours while slower processing times may cause delays and decreased performance. Therefore, the measurement of the execution time is important for the overall evaluation and the spherical assessment of an algorithm.

TABLE III
SYNTHETIC DATA RMSE ATE

Extractor	<i>Complex</i>	<i>Loops</i>	<i>Highway</i>	<i>Slope</i>	<i>Environment</i>	<i>Traffic</i>	<i>Rural</i>
SIFT	9.43	14.36	23.29	17.26	13.16	7.28	12.95
SP	10.24	13.67	7.4	11.77	14.73	7.31	13.15
R2D2	15.02	13.27	27.52	14.69	14.21	7.26	13.07
CD	16.03	32.25	25.5	16.43	30.0	7.09	15.14
DISK	10.04	14.82	24.91	failed	19.61	7.49	13.39
D2-Net	16.63	16.6	31.33	23.65	30.81	8.37	28.51
Key.Net	30.92	14.92	30.94	38.41	19.48	9.28	27.53

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Synthetic Data

The RMSE of ATE for each algorithm tested in the seven scenarios of CarlaSCENES described above is shown in Table III. The only geometric-based feature extractor tested, SIFT, outperforms the other algorithms in three of the seven sequences. SuperPoint also performs quite well, giving the best results in two sequences. In particular, it performs much better in the highway case, suggesting that the algorithm is more robust to high-speed camera displacements. From the above, we cannot draw any conclusion about the superiority of Deep Learning-based algorithms in scenarios that are problematic for traditional visual odometry approaches.

B. Real Data

Table IV shows the results of experiments performed with real data from KITTI. The results show that we have mixed results that do not allow us to easily identify the best solution. For example, ContextDesc gives the lowest RMSE ATE in two of the four sequences, while SIFT and SuperPoint consistently give good results. It is important to note that certain algorithms, such as D2-Net, were not able to complete all sequences because they lost tracking and required reinitialization.

TABLE IV
KITTI DATA RMSE ATE

Extractor	<i>03</i>	<i>04</i>	<i>09</i>	<i>10</i>
SIFT	1.12	0.29	47.54	4.03
SP	2.7	0.65	33.2	11.19
R2D2	33.97	0.29	47.85	failed
CD	2.84	0.12	31.63	7.5
DISK	failed	0.28	54.42	23.93
D2-Net	33.97	failed	failed	failed
Key.Net	1.07	0.22	55.06	5.12

C. Execution Time

The final benchmark for comparison is the duration of feature and descriptor extraction. Notably, the timings presented in Table V exclude any delays except for keypoint detection and descriptor creation. SuperPoint emerges as the most quick solution and can effectively fulfill real-time demands by operating at a rate exceeding 20 frames per second.

TABLE V
EXECUTION TIMES IN SECONDS

SIFT	SP	R2D2	CD	DISK	D2-Net	Key.Net
0.08	0.04	0.27	0.69	0.23	0.16	0.98

V. CONCLUSION

Autonomous vehicles rely heavily on accurate localization, and in recent years, deep learning-based techniques have become increasingly popular for this purpose. However, there is still a need for extensive testing of these techniques in real-world autonomous scenarios. In our study, we compared various popular algorithms that integrate deep learning-based feature extractors into SLAM systems, using both real and synthetic data to simulate odometry corner cases. Our findings revealed that only a few of these algorithms could match the accuracy of a well-known model-based algorithm. We've gone a step further by developing a simulation framework that not only generates multi-modal sensory data but also simulates realistic automotive scenarios. These scenarios can accurately depict odometry corner cases and facilitate in combination with ROS the study of lifelong and federated learning-based deep learning components within SLAM systems.

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